

LANGUAGE AS A MEAN FOR CULTURAL EXPOSURE AND COMMUNICATION

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Annotation. The article provides an overview of recent foreign research on the influence of bilingualism on the socio-cognitive development of personality. Recently, they have not only destroyed the myth about the dangers of bilingual development of children, but also shown that it gives much more than just knowledge of two languages. Based on a comparative analysis, the advantages of children and adults who have been in a bilingual environment since birth are shown. These advantages lie in the presence of metalinguistic abilities, which allow, in particular, to increase the speed of learning; in better executive development than monolingual peers functions (executive control, attention, ability to plan actions, concentration, suppression of unimportant information), important not only for performing verbal tasks, but also for managing any activity. The influence of bilingualism on cognitive decentration, the ability to learn other languages, and the formation of a high degree of social sensitivity, related to both to verbal and non-verbal communication (interpretation of facial expressions, gestures, intonation) and expressed in the most adequate reaction to the speech and communicative behavior of others.

Keywords: *Key words: bilingualism, cognitive development, executive functions, decentration, bilingual child.*

Аннотация. В статье дается обзор последних зарубежных исследований, посвященных влиянию билингвизма на социо-когнитивное развитие личности. Экспериментальные научные изыскания, предпринятые в последнее время, не только разрушили миф о вреде двуязычного развития детей, но и показали, что оно дает намного больше, чем просто знание двух языков. На основе сравнительного анализа показаны преимущества детей и взрослых, с рождения находящихся в билингвальной среде. Данные преимущества заключаются в наличии металингвистических способностей, позволяющих, в частности, увеличить скорость обучения; в более лучшем, чем у сверстников-монолингвов, развитии исполнительных функций (исполнительного контроля, внимания, умения планировать действия, концентрации, подавления несущественной информации), важных не только для выполнения вербальных задач, но и для управления любой деятельностью. Показано также влияние билингвизма на когнитивную децентрацию, способность к изучению других языков, на формирование высокой степени социальной чуткости, относящейся как к вербальной, так и к невербальной

коммуникации (интерпретация мимики, жестов, интонации) и выражающейся в наиболее адекватной реакции на речь и коммуникативное поведение окружающих.

Ключевые слова: *Ключевые слова: билингвизм, когнитивное развитие, исполнительные функции, децентрация, двуязычный ребенок.*

Annotatsiya. Maqolada ikki tillilikning shaxsning ijtimoiy-kognitiv rivojlanishiga ta'siri bo'yicha so'nggi xorijiy tadqiqotlarga umumiy nuqtai nazar berilgan. Yaqinda o'tkazilgan eksperimental ilmiy tadqiqotlar nafaqat bolalarning ikki tilli rivojlanishining xavfliligi haqidagi afsonani yo'q qildi, balki bu nafaqat ikki tilni bilishni ham ko'rsatdi. Qiyosiy tahlil asosida tug'ilgandan beri ikki tilli muhitda bo'lgan bolalar va kattalarning afzalliklari ko'rsatilgan. Ushbu afzalliklar, xususan, o'rganish tezligini oshirishga imkon beradigan metallingvistik qobiliyatlarning mavjudligidadir; ijro funktsiyalarini yaxshiroq rivojlantirishda (ijroiya nazorati, e'tibor, harakatlarni rejalashtirish qobiliyati, diqqatni jamlash, ahamiyatsiz ma'lumotlarni bostirish), bir tilli tengdoshlarga qaraganda nafaqat og'zaki vazifalarni bajarish, balki har qanday faoliyatni boshqarish uchun ham muhimdir. Ikki tillilikning kognitiv desentratsiyaga, boshqa tillarni o'rganish qobiliyatiga va og'zaki va og'zaki bo'lmagan muloqotga (yuz ifodalarini, imo-ishoralarni, intonatsiyani talqin qilish) bog'liq bo'lgan yuqori darajadagi ijtimoiy sezgirlikni shakllantirishga ta'siri va unga eng adekvat munosabatda ifodalangan. nutq va kommunikativ xatti-harakat sizning atrofingizdagilarga ham ko'rsatiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: *ikki tillilik, kognitiv rivojlanish, ijro etuvchi funktsiyalar, desentratsiya, ikki tilli bola.*

Introduction. Learning foreign languages is undoubtedly beneficial for an activity that broadens one's horizons and the boundaries of one's worldview, and growing up in a bilingual environment, being influenced by two languages from the first days of life, is generally a great success. Recent research on bilingualism has not only destroyed ideas about its harm, but also showed that the bilingual development of children gives much more than just knowledge of two languages. Along with the well-known differences of bilinguals, such as biculturalism, greater tolerance towards other cultures and an absolute superiority in competitiveness in the labor market, bilinguals have less known, but perhaps more important advantages, expressed in the way they think about and act in different situations.

Bilinguals have an intuitive sense of the structure and functioning of languages. This category of children uses two different linguistic systems that are identified in one conceptual system. Moving from one linguistic code on the other, they give an assessment of the situation that is appropriate to the context. Knowledge of a second language contributes to the awareness of the arbitrary connection that exists between a word and its meaning, and influences cognitive processing of form and content: makes selecting and encoding information easier and faster. This is partly due to the presence of two names for each item, and also with the ability to express the same idea in two different ways. L. S. Vygotsky wrote: "The separation of meaning from sound, words from things,

thoughts from words are necessary steps in the history of the development of concepts" [1].

In addition, an intuitive understanding of the structure of language helps bilinguals in the future and in learning other languages. Some of the abilities of bilingual children are associated with better compared with peers, executive control, responsible for attention, concentration, and suppression of irrelevant information. Bilinguals are easier than monolinguals to move from one task to another where selective attention and the ability to ignore interfering factors are required.

This superiority continues into adulthood. Main the factor linking bilingualism to executive control is due to the fact that bilinguals have both languages activated at all times. In this regard, a mechanism of inhibition (suppression) develops, which makes it possible to differentiate these languages, limiting the interference of the unused language in the used one. Thus, the practice of inhibiting one language while using another affects any activity requiring attention and executive control, enhancing the ability to perform multiple cognitive tasks simultaneously or in rapid succession. Constantly comparing shades of meaning and different grammatical forms, concentrating on one or the other language, analysis of languages and elimination of interference between them strengthen the bilingual's attentional abilities.

The advantage of bilinguals is explained by their abilities in the selection and monitoring (current control) of stimuli: the ability select only what is relevant in a given context. When languages are used alternately, they must activate one of them and suppress the other, according to the situation. For someone who grows up learning two languages at the same time, such transitions come naturally. These children develop more flexible language acquisition strategies from birth. The brain of a bilingual child is more plastic due to greater training, since it must distinguish between stimuli coming from different linguistic systems and prevent interference between them. Such children are able to more quickly control various linguistic stimuli even before they learn to speak, and, thanks to this, learn the fundamental properties of the languages of both parents, and therefore, easily manage various language systems.

Passive brain training during the first months of life allows bilingual children to put less effort into thinking and storing information, which affects the speed of learning. The above and other scientific studies refute doubts about the possibility of mixing languages and the later appearance of speech in bilinguals. "Even if a bilingual child had to learn twice as many words as his monolingual counterpart, he would not show any delay in the development of linguistic abilities. Pronounces his first words in the same way as monolingual children: the first word at about one year of age and the first 50 words at about eighteen months."

Late bilinguals acquire a second language during adolescence or as adults. A number of authors believe that between the ages of 6 and 12 years a child already realizes that a second language is inaccessible to him. Therefore, it is a common belief that one can only be bilingual after puberty.

Thus, a “weak” language must go through a “critical period of language acquisition.” Bilinguals are also classified based on their language skills. Language skills are divided into four areas: reading, writing, comprehension and speaking. However, bilinguals are least likely to learn to write and read in a second language, and therefore the level of mastery of language skills is determined by comprehension and speaking. Therefore, the following classification of bilingualism in children has been proposed[2]:

- passive;
- dominant;
- balanced;
- semilingual (semi-bilingualism).

Passive bilingualism is when a child is only able to understand his second language. This is generally considered to be the minimum requirement for bilingualism. Dominant bilingualism implies that bilingual children tend to be more proficient in one of the two languages. Typically, bilingual children have one “weak” language and one “strong” language. In a “weak” language, they tend to have trouble finding the right words and use code-mixing or code-switching more often than in a “strong” language. The “strong” language is the dominant language (Genesee et al., 2004), but depending on the situation in which the child lives, this dominance may change. Particularly when the child's environment is heavily dominated by one language and the second language is not supported well enough or is no longer needed (Grosjean, 2010). Because bilingual children have a “weak” and a “strong” language, they will demonstrate deficits in their non-dominant language. But once the environment changes and the child is exposed to a “weak” language (for example, when he is with his parents in a country where that language is spoken), then he will be capable of a sufficient level of proficiency in the non-dominant language as a means of communication. Balanced bilingualism implies equal proficiency in two languages. In general, the concept of balanced bilingualism is quite idealized and in fact rarely exists in reality.

Conclusion. To sum up, researchers studying the issues of bilingualism speak out about the positive impact of bilingualism on both the cognitive and communicative development of children, which is important for the development of modern society and the labor market. In accordance with age, bilinguals can be differentiated into early and late bilinguals, depending on their language skills (mainly in the area of understanding and speaking), as well as on the basis of their knowledge of elements of ethnic cultures. It has been shown that there is no single universal method for measuring language skills in bilingual children. It is advisable for specialists in preschool educational institutions to know about the characteristics of bilingualism in children and its impact on the development of cognitive and communicative characteristics in order to be more competent in creating conditions for the development of language competencies.

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